

Manual of stakeholder mapping and engagement

Deliverable 5.1

D5.1. Manual of stakeholder mapping and engagement

Summary

This deliverable summarises and discusses the strategy of B-WaterSmart for stakeholder mapping and engagement. It is aligned with the constitution of the Communities of Practice (CoP), as well as the strategic vision of the Living Labs (LL), and the water-smartness definition of the project. The objective of this manual is to offer detailed guidance that can be applied to projects on water sustainability and circular economy, in support of a broad engagement of social and institutional actors, as well as mutual learning and the co-creation of innovative sustainable solutions. This will require the integration of diverse sources of knowledge, social and economic concerns, taking into account the diversity of territories in Europe, and ultimately contributing towards climate adaptation and innovative models of governance, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SGD), the Green Deal, the Paris Agreement and the plan Next Generation EU.

The manual, which is aimed at a broad audience – including policy-makers, researchers, non-governmental organisations (NGO) and the public at large – provides an introduction to the key current challenges in the fields of water and sustainability; summarises the best practices and offers guidance on mapping stakeholders in projects related to sustainability and circular economy; and finally offers recommendations and useful references for planning a process of stakeholder engagement across these fields and beyond.

Deliverable number	Work package
D5.1.	WP5
Lead beneficiary	Deliverable author(s)
Institute of Social Sciences of the University of Lisbon (ICS-UL)	Carla Gomes (ICS-UL) Rosário Oliveira (ICS-UL) Luísa Schmidt (ICS-UL) Marcella Melo (ICS-UL) Margarida Rebelo (LNEC) Maria José Amores; Laura Flores (CET) Sigrid Damman (SINTEF) Alexandra Schmuck, Clemens Strehl (IWW) Stefania Munaretto; Lisa Andrews (KWR)
Quality assurance	
ICS-UL LNEC Ethics Advisor	Ana Delicado João Craveiro Maria do Céu Patrão Neves

Planned delivery date	Actual delivery date
30/06/2021	30/06/2021
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU = Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP = Restricted to other programme participants <input type="checkbox"/> RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium. Please specify: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

Table of contents

List of Figures	V
List of Tables.....	VI
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	VII
Executive summary	8
1 State of the art: challenges for water and society	9
1.1 Recent developments and new challenges	10
1.1.1 Circular economy.....	10
1.1.2 Sectoral integration and nexus approach	12
1.1.3 Beyond the social: nature-based solutions	13
1.2. Engaging stakeholders in the water sector.....	15
1.2.1. Adaptive water governance	16
1.2.2. Closing the loop: co-creating innovative solutions	22
2. Guidelines for stakeholder engagement	24
2.1. Step 1: identify.....	24
2.2. Step 2: analyse	26
2.3. Step 3: plan.....	33
2.3.1. Communication channels and participatory methodologies	37
3. Ethical issues: check list and key resources.....	40
4. Conclusions	42
5. References	43

List of Figures

Figure 1 - OECD Principles of Water Governance	17
Figure 2 - Eight conditions for adaptive governance in the case of coastal zones	19
Figure 3 - Governance framework	22
Figure 4 - Steps for implementing stakeholder engagement	24
Figure 5 - Rationale, typology, and methods for stakeholder analysis	28
Figure 6 - The Alignment, Interest and Influence Matrix	29
Figure 7 - Sources of knowledge for co-production	35

List of Tables

Table 1 - Methods for stakeholder analysis	30
Table 2 - Roles and typologies of stakeholders in B-WaterSmart CoPs	36
Table 3 - Participatory tools and techniques	38
Table 4 - Ethics procedures and sources	41

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
CoP	Communities of Practice
ESS	Ecosystem services
EC	European Commission
LL	Living Labs
NBS	Nature-based solutions
NGO	Non-governmental Organisations
GBI	Green and Blue Infrastructure
FWEN	Nexus Food-Water-Energy
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SES	Social–ecological systems

Executive summary

This manual is the first deliverable issued by WP5 – Society, Governance, Policy, which summarises and discusses the strategy of B-WaterSmart for stakeholder mapping and engagement. It is aligned with the constitution of the Communities of Practice in the project (WP1, D1.1. - CoPs Architecture and Stakeholder Mapping for each LL), as well as the strategic agenda of the Living Labs (WP1) and the water-smartness definition of the project (WP6).

The objective of this manual is to offer an overview of best practices that can be applied to projects on water sustainability and circular economy, in support of a broad engagement of social and institutional actors, as well as co-learning and co-creation of innovative sustainable solutions. This will require the integration of diverse sources of knowledge, social and economic concerns, taking into account the diversity of territories across Europe, and ultimately contributing towards climate adaptation and innovative models of governance, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), the Green Deal, Paris Agreement and the recovery plan EU Next Generation.

The manual is aimed at a broad audience – including policy-makers, researchers, NGOs and the public at large and does not intend to provide a detailed description of the stakeholder engagement process in B-WaterSmart, already the main content of D1.1., which details the process of constituting the CoP, as well as the key stakeholders to be involved in each LL and the participatory methods to apply in CoP meetings. It proposes instead, using the example of this H2020 project, to provide an introduction to the key current challenges in the fields of water and sustainability, reviewing the best practices on mapping stakeholders in projects related to sustainability, water governance and circular economy (section 1.1.), and introducing the model of adaptive water governance (section 1.2.) and its main challenges in achieving a broad participation of multiple stakeholders, while ensuring an effective implementation of innovative solutions, as well as flexibility to adapt to environmental changes.

The deliverable then offers recommendations and useful references for planning a process of stakeholder engagement (section 2), through the steps of stakeholder identification, analysis and planning. It includes a brief section and check list with useful resources to assess and manage the ethics issues and procedures to follow in such processes of stakeholder engagement (section 3).

1 State of the art: challenges for water and society

Water scarcity is one of the major challenges facing society on a global scale. The problem of insufficient water supply is not confined to traditionally water scarce countries in the Middle East or the Global South, but even countries with previously sufficient water supplies are being affected, since there is an increasing gap between demand and availability of existing water resources due to climate change, growing population, and limited access to new conventional water resources.

Water scarcity is becoming a serious issue across the European Union as well as globally in terms of quantity (e.g. limited access to new conventional water resources) and quality (e.g. contamination of water resources). In the next decades, water stress is likely to continue to intensify due to multiple factors such as climate change (changes in precipitation patterns, higher frequency and severity of droughts, higher irrigation demands) and regional economic and/or population growth (leading to increased water demand for industrial and domestic purposes). According to the [European Environment Agency](#), the area and population exposed to water scarcity conditions has been increasing in Europe, and rises up to 20% of the area and more than 30% of the population during the Summer. The Mediterranean region is particularly affected, with approximately 20% of the population living under constant water stress.

Thus, alternative water resources, such as reclaimed water from treated municipal wastewater fit-for-purpose, are increasingly considered as reliable alternatives to satisfy water demand. The EU regulation No. 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse for agricultural irrigation, which entered into force in May 2020, is one of the most recent key responses of the European Commission (EC) to the issue of worsening water scarcity.

Pollution and the decline in water quality can also increase water scarcity. Pollutants may be introduced via diverse sources, amongst others surface runoff, agricultural runoff or stormwater runoff. Even if the water resource may still be usable for the abstraction of drinking water, the cost and/or level of treatment may increase, thus making the use of the water resource economically or technically unfeasible. Climate change can in fact stimulate systemic innovation that will also address some of the outlined stressors in a traditionally rather conservative field (Widener, Gliedt, & Hartman, 2017).

The coming decade will be a turning point in facing the challenges related to climate change and the socio-economic crisis left on the wake of the current pandemics of COVID-19. The B-WaterSmart project aims at facing these challenges and supporting the implementation of current EU policy for sustainable development, most notably the new EU Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (2020), the Green Deal (2019), the Action Plan for the Circular Economy (2020) and the post-COVID resilience strategy New Generation EU, along with the national Resilience Plans and the Water Directives & Regulations, including the new Drinking Water Directive (2020), which was prompted by an European Citizens' Initiative, "[Right2Water](#)", a perfect example of a far-reaching 'bottom-up' initiative in the water sector. The European Commission recently took a stand on stakeholder involvement for success in complying with the European Green Deal as well as committing itself to a more sustainable 2030 agenda (Camilleri, 2020).

A project such as B-WaterSmart, one of the five projects approved in H2020 within the topic call Building a water-smart economy and society (TOPIC ID: CE-SC5-04-2019), seizes this momentum in engaging a wide range of stakeholders, across the nexus water-energy-resources-waste, in co-creating innovative solutions to face these challenges and secure water access and quality for the

generations to come, starting with the implementation of widely participated Communities of Practice that will operate in network across the project, but also adapt to the specificities and challenges of each territory. Not just across Europe, based on its six Living Labs – Alicante, Flanders, East Frisia, Bodo, Lisbon, Venice – but also beyond Europe through its replication efforts that will ensure a consistent impact of the project.

1.1 Recent developments and new challenges

1.1.1 Circular economy

Conventional practices of water management in urban settings are currently characterised as an ‘open loop’ (i.e. most water is abstracted, used once, and discarded, ideally after treatment). Water reuse practices can close this loop, thereby helping to preserve water resources and achieve compliance with the principles of circular economy, also in the water sector.

Over the next few decades, and particularly until 2030, it is crucial to transform our patterns of production and consumption, services and infrastructure into a more circular economic model, which makes the most of the available endogenous resources, contributing to climate adaptation, strengthening resilience of territories and societies, while striving to fulfil the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This will require shifts in governance and policy that substantially transform the current paradigm of economic growth. In addition, the circular economy (CE) can bring opportunities for a more balanced socioeconomic development, as well as reducing dependency on non-renewable sources (Lokesh et al., 2018).

The different social and environmental problems faced by society, such as pollution, climate change, intense urbanisation, and population growth, need to be addressed towards this transformation into sustainability, which requires that production and management of resources be carried out in a circular way, by minimising waste and re-integrating the resources into the value chain as much as possible. In fact, the CE proposes a path of looking at natural and human cycles to incorporate the elements that are constantly removed and modified back into the production chain. In addition, it aims to reduce the use of raw resources, incorporating elements back into biological cycles.

Circular Economy has emerged as a paradigm, highlighting multiple paths and targets to attain sustainable development, and to propose ways to create value for costumers, societies, and other stakeholders. It aims to close cycles that are currently thought of in a linear way, that is, the productive logic assumes new materials taken from nature will always be used to produce new goods without thinking about their disposal. The CE rationality presupposes that discarded materials are reincorporated into the production and consumption cycles.

The idea, when employing policies and practices that promote the CE, is to place value on both materials taken from nature and those discarded, in addition to promote a responsible use of them. The direct contribution of the CE is in reducing the pressure on the environment, in the air, in water and on land, favouring the achievement of some SDGs (e.g. clean water and sanitation for all (SDG6), responsible consumption and production (SDG12), climate action (SDG 13), life below water (SDG 14) and life on land (SDG15). The [EU Circular Economy Action Plan for a Cleaner and More](#)

Competitive Europe assumes as a core objective the adoption of the CE in order to obtain the preservation of European natural resources¹.

Cities and regions are at the frontlines in implementing a CE model, as a stimulus to promote sustainable development and strengthen resilience to environmental change. In order to promote and accelerate this circular transition it is important to follow and monitor city plans, resources, products and services across all stages of their life cycle, as well as better articulate the management of water resources across urban and rural territories.

One of the main targets of city plans in terms of sustainability is to become climate-neutral through changing the way society produces and consumes, and by empowering end-users. To this aim, social innovations, eco-innovations, sharing economy initiatives, the level of greening of the main economic sectors, the implementation of new business models, eco-design and sustainable building initiatives need to be monitored (Avdiushchenko, 2018). Special focus and consideration has to be given to material footprints, additional critical sectors (e.g., constructions, plastics, textiles, and electronics), the design of sustainable products, innovation, added-value change and its implication for the climate neutrality ambition of the EU (OECD, 2020).

The water cycle in the city's water supply has been mostly linear, which means that the water used in the system will be released polluted to the sewer system where it will receive treatment, and then be directly returned to a natural course or the sea (Stuchtey, 2015). However, under a CE model, the urban water cycle is to gradually re-incorporate influents such as retained, harvested and recycled water, into the consumption chain, protecting sources of freshwater from overexploitation.

The process of developing a CE for water – addressing environmental degradation and resource scarcity - involves the development of new technologies and engineering, to generate a more intelligent chain across the water-energy-resources-waste nexus. A fundamental part of this process is the involvement and cooperation of citizens and stakeholders in decision-making processes. Social aspects are relevant in CE since they can give an overview on how strategies and actions impact or benefit society (Padilla Rivera et al 2020).

In the case of B-WaterSmart, the focus is on coastal cities and regions, with their particular issues and challenges. Intense urbanisation brings about challenges for the built environment (e.g. in the production of waste and water contamination). In this sense, cities are seen as the fundamental stage for the demonstration of CE business models and solutions. Circular opportunities will be identified for the 6 LLs, supporting the development of new business models. The operators of these business models, including industries, agriculture companies and water utilities, will be active stakeholders during the whole project and were identified in the report “Manual of Data Specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs” (D4.1).

¹ European Commission (2020a). Towards a Circular Economy. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/jobs-growth-and-investment/towards-circular-economy_en (accessed on 12 May 2020).

1.1.2 Sectoral integration and nexus approach

Circular economy therefore brings a new approach towards production chains, requiring a novel perspective on the way we deal with the production and consumption of goods. Increasingly the interconnections between different sectors (e.g., wastewater treatment and industry) need to be thought as part of the same dynamic, along the nexus water-energy-resources-waste.

In this sense, it is important to approach the nexus water-energy-resources-waste from a holistic perspective, including the management of agriculture and ecosystems in an integrated manner, acknowledging the peculiarities of each cycle. It is important to think about all this integration from a multisectoral point of view but also through a bio-based approach, in order to place natural means as a fundamental part to be preserved with the introduction of a CE that values ecosystems and the services they provide.

It is crucial to include stakeholders in the decision-making processes from an early stage, starting with those that will play a central role as operators of CE business models that integrate multiple sectors across the nexus, by implementing solutions that save energy, reuse materials and products, as well as saving raw materials and natural resources for the next generations. In the case of B-WaterSmart, the requisites for the integration of this type of stakeholders are outlined in [D4.1. – Manual of Data Specifications Required for Mapping of Actors at the Living Labs](#), which provides a preliminary identification of actors across sectors (e.g. industry, agriculture) and their possible synergies in terms of circular opportunities along the nexus water-energy-resources-waste.

The nexus Food-Water-Energy (FWEN) has also achieved considerable prominence across academic research and policy sectors as one of the possible frameworks to assess an integrated model to look into the urban complexity. The nexus sets an imperative for integrated management and policymaking, centring on the potential trade-offs and complementarities between interdependent food, water and energy systems (Benson, 2020).

Policymaking should thus integrate different elements (e.g., plans, guidelines, strategies, frameworks) in the FWEN when trying to develop nature-based solutions (NBS) towards sustainable urban development, since links between research and urban planning are quite limited. This could help avoid unintended consequences, e.g. water contamination as a side product of urban agriculture or increased water and energy demands for green space or food production. Meanwhile, there can be co-benefits as well, e.g., green roofs that control for storm runoff and also bring about cooling effects; urban wetlands that help clean wastewater and reduce urban heat island formation. In addition to their contribution to the quality of life, urban GBI can promote greater resilience in urban areas, thus altering their capacity to deal with growing environmental and socioeconomic issues. Thus, the management of urban GBI must be connected to the socio-ecological dynamics of each location or region, with their cultural, economic, and political specificities jointly guiding the development of a goal-based GBI-FWEN framework. In this way, policy goal setting should take into consideration the possible synergies and trade-offs associated to a variety of pathways in the GBI-FWEN links, while the effective evaluation of certain GBI development should take into account their impact on multiple elements jointly. These recommendations follow the mainstream of urban GBI, ecosystem services, and FWEN literatures (Bellezoni et al., 2021).

1.1.3 Beyond the social: nature-based solutions

Many concepts closer to a “water cycle thinking” in delivering water services draw the connection to nature-based solutions, often also referred to as green infrastructure. NBS can be defined as “solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience; such solutions bring more diverse natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions.” It further emphasizes that “NBS must benefit biodiversity and support the delivery of a range of ecosystem services.” (EC, 2020b).

The NBS concept builds on a distinctive set of premises: (i) some societal challenges stem from human activities that have failed to recognize ecological limitations; (ii) sustainable alternatives to those activities can be found by looking to nature for design and process knowledge. They are seen as positive responses to societal challenges, with the potential to simultaneously meet environmental, social and economic objectives, and as such linked with a systemic approach emphasizing the need to work beyond 'silos' and systematically involve stakeholders across disciplines and sectors, including citizens (Horizon 2020 Expert Group, 2015).

Nesshöver et al. (2017) highlight that more widespread use of NBS will require substantial institutional change, given that critical decisions about NBS design, costs, location and scale as well as levels of management intensity in most cases will involve a wide range of stakeholders (and, one may add, these may also constitute new constellations of stakeholders). On this background, they propose five steps to consider in NBS projects:

Dealing with uncertainty and complexity: drawing on e.g. adaptive management to devise flexible ways to maximize learning opportunities, and considering practices as experiments. In addition to the societal context, and where feasible, socio-ecological modelling should be considered in a transdisciplinary learning process, where approaches to problems and solutions, including values and goals, are deliberated by experts, practitioners and stakeholders.

Ensuring the involvement of multiple stakeholders: broad participation can bring valuable knowledge to NBS planning and management, as well as make the process more acceptable, increase legitimacy and generally support democracy.

Ensuring the sound use of multi- and transdisciplinary knowledge: including closer collaboration across disciplines as well as a two-way flow between practical action and science, in order to better understand socio-ecological interactions.

Developing a common understanding of multifunctional solutions, trade-offs and natural adaptation: consider the environmental and social complexity of each territory, defining objectives, selecting appropriate solutions and performance standards through social negotiation.

Evaluate and monitor for mutual learning: as NBS often deal with problems manifest at different spatial scales, evaluation and monitoring must take a nested approach. Certain solutions and aspects may be monitored in a short time-span and in connection with locally specific challenges, but when considering larger geographical scales, the temporal scale of evaluation will increase, as will the specificity of predefined goals. Therefore, NBS evaluation requires a coordinated processing and communication across scales, by use of participatory evaluative and co-development approaches.

Nature-based solutions present a credible means to address key societal issues, such as climate change, disaster risk and biodiversity loss. The EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change recently updated (COM/2021/82) highlights NBS as a cross-cutting priority area to support the further development and implementation of climate adaptation strategies at all levels of governance (EC, 2021). Targeted NBS interventions are capable of enabling a more comprehensive implementation of the Floods Directives, Ground Water Directive and Urban Waste-Water Framework Directive. The overarching Water Framework Directive benefits directly or indirectly from NBS by integrating water management in terms of quality and quantity, as well as promote an active participation of stakeholders through the co-design of NBS measures for water scarcity.

In the urbanisation era we live in, urban development leads to changes in the surface cover that disrupt the hydrological cycle of cities, which is increasingly raising the notability of the NBS approach in policy and academia. In many cases, urban Green and Blue Infrastructure (GBI)² is a way to respond to the resilience of urban ecosystems by providing services to maintain or restore hydrological functions.

GBI implies proactively adaptive planning and management models, as a response to uncertainty and as soon as an option to effectively harness resilience. In this context, it is imperative that NBS implementation includes provisions to enable this adaptive planning and management, generating evidence-base provided by monitoring and evaluation, drawing on local knowledge as well as on scientific understanding (Zölch *et al.*, 2017).

Stakeholders should clearly comprehend how GBI and FWE systems are interconnected in urban areas, aiming to promote the sustainability of cities. Despite being ultimately related to human well-being, urban GBI is unlikely to help drive change if their positive effects are not well communicated to stakeholders (i.e. by better connecting with decision-makers, emphasizing participatory approaches, and contributing to capacity building) (Bellezoni *et al.*, 2021, Zölch *et al.*, 2017).

A greater integration across the local, regional and national scales can promote the positive effects of GBI on the planning of FWEN systems beyond city limits. The advancement of the desired sustainability in the use of scarce resources should not necessarily depend on national policies and initiatives. Smaller and more achievable goals that are closer to citizens can be better accepted by the community, bringing the feeling of being part of a change that can be observed on a small scale. NBS are a consequence and cause of changing attitudes towards sustainability in cities and their development shows that urban planning, political will, and social participation must always be intertwined to make cities a better place for living.

Especially in the water sector, many concepts can be found which try to integrate or take advantage of nature to deliver water services. Water services itself are defined by the WFD (2000) as “all services which provide for households, public institutions or any economic activity: (a) abstraction, impoundment, storage, treatment and distribution of surface water or groundwater, (b) waste water collection and treatment facilities which subsequently discharge into surface water.” This is a view followed by EurEau (2020), which defines drinking water treatment, collection and treatment of waste

² Blue infrastructure refers to water elements, like rivers, canals, ponds, wetlands, floodplains, water treatment facilities, etc. Green infrastructure refers to trees, parks, fields, forests, etc. These terms originated in urban and land-use planning.

water as water services. Additionally, rain water management (storm water), flood protection and reclaimed water provision is provided by some water service utilities in Europe (EurEau 2020).

From the perspective of the Circular Economy, the delivery of ecosystem services is a key element of NBS. Ecosystem services (ESS) are the contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being (Potschin and Haines-Young 2016). The application of the ESS concept in water management is increasing (Gerner et al. 2018, Anzaldua et al. 2018). ESS assessments based on available tools and knowledge are necessary to value the various benefits of NBS against its costs and efforts for implementation (decision support for policy, practice and water management). NBS have the potential to deliver multiple benefits, such as climate change mitigation, biodiversity, improvements in water quality and waterbody conditions, flood mitigation and coastal resilience, micro climate regulation and air quality to name a few, which are linked to the water cycle (EC 2020). Consequently, to date, NBS and its ecosystem services have found its way in many EU policies already, either explicitly or implicitly (Bouwma et al., 2018).

The Nature4cities project (H2020) developed a step-by-step guide for the co-production and co-creation of NBS with stakeholders. The guide sees both the interventions and their outcomes as contingent on interactions between a) contextual conditions (infrastructural, physical, organizational and socio-economic and socio-cultural) and b) the project planners and stakeholders (including end users and citizens) involved in NBS planning and implementation. The approach is user centric and considers citizen engagement as a necessary transversal aspect of the planning process.

The eight-step procedure (Breukers and Jeuken, 2017) emphasizes that the success of NBS, to a large extent, depends on how well it becomes embedded in a particular local geographical and social context. Articulating views about how the intervention 'fits' offers a starting point to discuss or negotiate acceptability, including discussions about costs, benefits and their distribution. Articulation and alignment of different visions and expectations is likewise considered as important, before further contextualising the problem and strategizing a multi-stakeholder approach (identify stakeholders (e.g., using a network mapping tool), create communication plan, create shared understanding of the common project). The next steps are planning with local stakeholders (engage them, review and adapt the planned NBS, develop a common action plan, test ideas), implementation (coordination and facilitation), maintenance (in continuing engagement with stakeholders), offer support and assistance, and finally, monitoring, improvement and evaluation, which includes development of a learning culture. A suite of more specific tools for application during the various steps (e.g. Citizens' Say communication tool, Implementation Models Database, Social Acceptance tool and more) is provided at the project website: <https://www.nature4cities.eu/results>.

1.2. Engaging stakeholders in the water sector

Stakeholder engagement has been widely applied and increasingly pointed as crucial for achieving relevant outcomes in water management. Stakeholder engagement has been increasingly implemented in the context of improving water governance, especially after the Eco Summit 1992, where the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development introduced norms for public involvement in decision-making processes. It followed the Dublin Statement on Water and Sustainable Development, which included participation as one of its guiding principles. Following this trend, the

Agenda 21 highlighted the use of public participation to ensure greater adherence to policies for the development of more effective legislation in the environmental area.

The SDG give emphasis to citizen participation at the local level, as well as a whole social agenda that encompasses social inclusion, gender equality, political coherence, integration among stakeholders, and other characteristics that define the context of social and environmental justice (Akhmouch & Clavreul, 2016). Two examples of other key documents that address processes of stakeholder engagement in the water sector are The European Water Framework Directive and the Aarhus Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making, and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters.

A weak engagement of stakeholders and citizens ultimately results in ineffective policies that don't address long-term environmental problems adequately (Wehn et al., 2018). Stakeholder engagement is individual to each context, dynamic, and one of the most challenging components of any management program, hence it is critical to prioritize in terms of financial and human resources (Conallin et al., 2017). This requires the integration of different sources of knowledge – including local or traditional knowledge - consideration of different local realities, and building trust amongst the stakeholders and institutions involved, in order to empower citizens and social groups, while ensuring equity in access to environmental benefits and natural resources (Reed, 2008).

Medema et al. (2017) outline the following key objectives for a process of stakeholder engagement:

- a) promote cooperation within the network;
- b) build up bridges between networks, governmental and non-governmental organisations;
- c) combine multiple knowledge sources usually dispersed amongst local, regional, and national agencies (and autonomous, where applicable);
- d) build capacity to support the development of new governance models;
- e) develop new knowledge and practices;
- f) integrate geographical and administrative scales;
- g) facilitate new knowledge, as well as new social practices and interactions.

1.2.1. Adaptive water governance

Romano & Akhmouch (2019) identified five different types of gaps in urban water management: administrative, policy, objective, information and accountability, to which a weak stakeholder engagement is one of the factors concurring. In order to overcome such gaps, water governance has been moving towards a 'bottom-up' approach (Conallin et al., 2017). Low stakeholder involvement in decisions leads to policy weaknesses that threaten significant structural changes such as the Sivens dam in France and new water charges in Ireland. In the case of Ireland, popular pressure was so intense that fees were cancelled and not implemented (Akhmouch & Clavreul, 2016).

In addition to legislative changes towards a more inclusive decision-making process, special initiatives have been set up to improve governance in the water sector. Such is the case of the OECD Water Governance Initiative, which established the key voluntary principles for water governance in 2015 (Figure 1) – around the key dimensions of Effectiveness, Efficiency, Trust and Engagement - along with the SDG, of which SDG 6 aims to 'Ensure access to water and sanitation for all'.

**Figure 1 - OECD Principles of Water Governance
(OECD, 2015)**

According to the OECD Water Governance Initiative, stakeholder engagement is one of the three pillars of water governance (effectiveness, efficiency, trust and engagement).

Borrowing learnings from ecology, over the last couple of decades a new approach emerged, the adaptive management of social-ecological systems (Folke, Berkes, & Colding, 1998; Walker, Holling, Carpenter, & Kinzig, 2004). Combined with scholarship on innovative governance, it gives rise to an approach that is crucial for facing water challenges today: adaptive governance. Only a flexible and innovative governance can respond to the ‘wicked’ problem of climate adaptation, which will be transversal to any notion of sustainable development in the present day and over the next decades.

Walker *et al.* (2004) consider that three attributes of social–ecological systems (SESs) determine their future trajectories: **resilience**, **adaptability**, and **transformability**. Resilience is the capacity of a system to absorb disturbance and reorganize while undergoing change so as to still retain essentially the same function, structure, identity, and feedbacks. Adaptability is the capacity of actors in the system to influence resilience (in a SES, essentially to manage it). Transformability is the capacity to create a fundamentally new system when ecological, economic, or social structures make the existing system untenable. Beyond resilience and adaptation, what is currently at stake is a broad transformation of social and political systems, in face of worsening climate scenarios. Transformability will require, in this context, to create new stability landscapes by “introducing new components and ways of making a living, thereby changing the state variables and often the scale that define the system”.

Adaptive governance, as a range of interactions between actors, networks, organisations, and institutions, emerges from the need to approach the management of SESs holistically and to

strengthen their resilience to change back to a desired state, or towards a new one, when they reorganise in response to changes such as policy windows, funding opportunities, and/or biophysical shocks to the system. This requires the creation of a multilevel governance structure, through networks of participation and experimentation, stimulating a culture of learning and reinforcing adaptive capacity at the bioregional scale, at which the governance structure best fits ecological function. It exists across a spectrum, from top-down to bottom-up, from rigid to flexible, from global to local (Chaffin, Gosnell, & Cosens, 2014)

Boundary territories such as coastal cities or river basins present particular challenges, in the sense that multiple and contrasting interests and demands converge to them. They are core territories for wealth generation, but at the same time have to balance the concurring demands of economic sectors and populations, including tourist seasonal populations and the requirements for ecosystem conservation. Traditional administrative and institutional structures typically face challenges in managing socio-environmental issues that are transboundary in nature. The emerging threats of the recent decades (population growth, water pollution, and most notably climate change) add to the tension that looms over these territories, and raises unprecedented challenges to the management of their natural resources.

In complex territories such as coastal zones, the perception of a common risk may well be the corollary of a new sense of community (Schmidt, Gomes, Guerreiro, & O'Riordan, 2014). One of the challenges to address will be, in the case of water governance, citizen's awareness of water scarcity and the need to create a sense of urgency and implement profound changes in socio-ecological systems and infrastructures, especially over the next decade (horizon 2030). Public awareness of water scarcity is amongst the key societal issues preliminary identified by the B-WaterSmart Living Labs. Taking due account of these social perceptions is determinant to inform stakeholder mapping and engagement in projects related to water governance.

It is in this complex and unprecedented scenario that we reflect on how to innovate in the governance of natural resources such as water, making 'bottom-up' innovation and co-production a reality, and making the most of all knowledge sources available.

While emphasizing the importance of a good coordination between stakeholders, Nicholson-Cole and O'Riordan (2009) also stress the need to pay more attention to political will and financial support, amongst the key barriers to overcome in implementing a model of adaptive governance (Figure 2). Furthermore, the implementation of any new decision or policy will have to address issues of social justice and fairness, at the distributive, procedural and recognition level, while building on local-based capabilities (Schlosberg, Collins, & Niemeyer, 2017).

Figure 2 - Eight conditions for adaptive governance in the case of coastal zones
(Nicholson-Cole and O'Riordan, 2009)

Huitema et al. (2009) identify four key elements of adaptive water governance: **polycentric governance, public participation, experimentation**, and a **bioregional approach**. In the case of water, the bioregional approach refers usually to governance systems that encompass river basins across regional or national boundaries. The ability to organise, monitor and negotiate the use of natural resources across administrative and political boundaries is undoubtedly one of the key challenges for adaptive water governance today.

Although these elements reinforce each other, there is also a need to recognise the tension and trade-offs between them. If a polycentric system of authority is apparently more welcoming of public participation in decisions, for instance, institutional accountability towards the public becomes more complex. In practice, it is more challenging to organise a process of public participation with multiple

“As stakeholders at different scales attempt to embark upon understanding what adaptation does mean and require, it is becoming clear that the scope for adaptation is larger than what is politically and institutionally deliverable in the short term.”
(Nicholson-Cole and O’Riordan, 2009, p. 12)

organisations involved in decision-making. Ultimately, they argue, the best approach is to find a balanced and pragmatic arrangement, making use of windows of opportunity and not waiting for optimal conditions. In the end, the goal is to make governance systems more resilient and better able to respond to change and uncertainty, while keeping them manageable.

Generally the development of bottom-up processes, with a wider involvement of civil society, has been stimulated in projects of water governance over the last couple of decades, but in fact there is still little empirical knowledge on the performance of different governance arrangements and the impact of different combinations of governance modes. That is why Pahl-Wostl et al. (2019) advocate for a combination of different governance styles (e.g., strengthening synergies and avoiding conflicts), and the evolution of polycentric and hybrid governance systems. Furthermore, the authors argue for the establishment of meta-governance mechanisms, i.e., a reflexive process of societal learning that allows to monitor the impact of governance arrangements in the sector, reflecting on values, norms and principles.

An adaptive governance model follows a coordinated and integrated approach to management, encompassing different scales of government as well as the participation of key actors for decision-making. Nicholson-Cole & O’Riordan (2009) locate social and institutional learning at the core of this process, considering that situations of success and failure of the engagement process can be quite beneficial for the whole process itself. It is also important to present a strong governance foundation, such as a thorough and careful preparation, solid scientific knowledge and trust building, towards achieving common views of future desirable scenarios, in face of accelerated environmental change.

According to Conallin (2017), an adaptive approach to the governance of natural resources is based on four components: learning, describing, predicting, and doing. The learning stage involves observation and evaluation to develop a framework that will contemplate the specific characteristics of the adaptive process. The description and prediction steps aim to generate information to guide the practices that will be performed in the making process. The process of joint construction, brought from the involvement of stakeholders, departing from their concerns, needs and specific demands, is what will lead to more relevant and effective outcomes.

The literature on water governance has made a distinction between bureaucratic hierarchies, networks and markets as the main governance modes. In bureaucratic hierarchies, regulatory processes are mainly based on formal institutions and governmental actors play the dominant role. Markets are based on a combination of formal and informal institutions, and non-state actors dominate. Networks – such as Communities of Practice - are largely governed by informal institutions and both state and non-state actors may participate (Pahl-Wostl, 2017).

The informality and high flexibility in membership makes networks interesting with respect to processes of learning and change, yet in other aspects they are more difficult to manage, for example in terms of accountability and binding commitments, for which formal regulations are needed. Therefore, balancing flexibility with some degree of formality will be the ideal, by developing hybrid and polycentric systems that combine decentralisation of power with an effective coordination among multiple centres of decision-making. These systems will support a process of transformative change, helping to enhance innovation, learning, adaptation, trust, cooperation and the achievement of more effective, equitable, and sustainable outcomes at multiple scales (Pahl-Wostl, 2017).

In sum, the move from a top-down hierarchic approach to a ‘bottom-up’ and adaptive governance is not without its challenges. Cosens and Gunderson (2018) highlight three major issues deserving special attention: (1) the lack of a clear legal mandate and appropriate structure for agency action to facilitate the preparation for, emergence of, and institutionalisation of the results of adaptive governance; (2) the lack of legal mechanisms to assure that a move from state-centric governmental control of environmental issues to state-enabled adaptive governance is not destabilising and does

not occur at the expense of legitimacy, accountability, equity, and justice; and (3) the lack of legal tools and a governmental structure necessary to empower governmental agencies to facilitate and participate while enhancing the participatory capacity of local actors to engage in adaptive governance.

Institutional inertia, path dependence and maladaptation are other possible limitations that may hinder the implementation of innovative and adaptive solutions across the water value chain (Scott, Shrestha, & Lutz-Ley, 2020). The authors note that 'path-dependent institutions' use concepts, knowledge or approaches rooted in the past to address novel or persistent challenges, and tend to frame new problems in similar ways or apply the same analytical techniques as in the past. Yet, they contend that the resilience of water infrastructure and institutions can be enhanced through a combination of hard-path and soft-path measures, building institutional collaboration for innovation, and using alternative planning and assessment tools. Again, the most feasible approach will require hybrid and complementing methods, as Pahl-Wostl (2017) had previously noted for modes of governance.

Jiménez et al. (2020) state that water governance is a combination between functions, performed with certain attributes, to achieve one or more desired outcomes, all shaped by the values and aspirations of individuals. They distinguish the following attributes:

Multilevel governance - implies that there are decision-making centres or governing authorities at different levels (vertical) or layers (horizontal i.e., arrangements that may not necessarily stand in hierarchical order but have a certain level of independence and interdependence between institutions within the same level of governance)

Participation - implies the meaningful and active involvement of a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including vulnerable or marginalised groups in decision making processes. Having the opportunities to influence decisions taken in the sector, along with the right to know how their inputs were considered, what decisions were made and implemented, and on what grounds

Deliberation - features mechanisms that facilitate open communication and discussion through mediums of debate, dissent, mediation and negotiation to create a common ground of collective action.

Inclusiveness - is recognising the rights of individuals and groups across different categories, needs and vulnerabilities, and without any kind of discrimination based on race, colour, age, gender, religious affiliation, ethnicity, language, disability, economic backgrounds or any other conditions of origin.

Accountability - refers to the principle whereby elected officials and those that have a responsibility in water services or water resources management account for their actions and answer to those they serve (in a case such as the B-WaterSmart project this refers to those responsible for other services across the water-energy-resources-waste nexus as well)

Transparency - refers to "openness and public access to information so that citizens can understand the decision-making processes that affect them, and are knowledgeable about the standards to expect from public officials.

Evidence-based decision-making - around water seeks to identify and leverage reliable technical and scientific, empirical and contextual evidence for decision-making.

Efficiency - in process management means that processes and institutions produce results that meet the needs of society, while making the best use of resources at their disposal.

Impartiality and rule of law - having legal frameworks and mechanisms that are designed and enforced impartially, in a fair and non-discriminatory manner, reflective of the human rights-based approach.

Adaptiveness - described as one of the attributes under adaptive governance in relation to resilience means the ability to self-organise, learn, respond, cope and use adaptive management strategies in situations of uncertainties, risk and nonlinearities.

Figure 3 - Governance framework
(Jimenez et al 2020, p. 15)

1.2.2. Closing the loop: co-creating innovative solutions

Knowledge co-production is undoubtedly today a core concept in any process of stakeholder engagement, but the integration of different sources of knowledge is challenging and poses practical issues. An effective recognition of alternative sources of knowledge (e.g., local knowledge or ethno-climatological knowledge) requires transparent procedures that ensure participants that their visions, values and contributions are in fact taken into consideration in decisions, in this case on water management. It is also of paramount importance for trust-building that stakeholders have an effective opportunity to influence decisions, along with the right to know how their inputs were considered (Jiménez et al., 2020)

Often even when organisations and procedures are designed to incorporate both scientific and experience-based knowledge into water management, in practice the emphasis on natural science prevails. In addition, the inclusion of experience-based knowledge is constrained by “both communicative problems and more general problems associated with participatory efforts, including peoples’ varying abilities and willingness to attend” (Lundmark & Jonsson, 2013). It is critical to acknowledge, in processes of stakeholder engagement and co-creation, the power differentials among members (between experts and non-experts), and that the relationship between water management

and knowledge is shaped by cognitive, cultural political and institutional factors that foster, constrain and intermediate the use of scientific and other forms of knowledge relationship (Lemos, 2015). Issues of power, equity, and justice are becoming increasingly important in tackling the water governance challenges exacerbated by the effects of climate change, industrialization, and urbanisation (Özerol et al., 2018).

The co-production approach has been considered fundamental to fostering community trust and awareness of climate risks (McNie, 2013), as well as ownership of sustainability initiatives (Dilling and Lemos, 2011). The co-production approach departs from users' needs in defining which information should be developed, and how. Social scientists, in this context, can act as information brokers, crucial nodes in these knowledge networks, helping to facilitate dialogue between stakeholders, exchanging information and adapting it to multiple audiences when appropriate (Hutchins et al., 2013).

In these new frameworks, science is integrated across social, environmental, physical and engineering disciplines; is transdisciplinary, that is, it straddles the science-policy divide; and is adaptive to account for complexity, acceleration, non-linearity and abrupt change. Similarly, emerging governance approaches that fit the complexity and integrated character of the problems they try to solve are adaptive, nested, and span scales of problems and jurisdictions; actively involve communities and stakeholders; and incorporate all kinds of knowledge to inform decision-making (Lemos, 2015).

Projects such as B-WaterSmart are anchored in the co-creation of innovative solutions with a wider involvement of stakeholders, and therefore the engagement process has to be planned in a way that allows for the discussion of user's needs, from an early stage, as well as their direct participation in the development and adjustment of technical solutions and policies. This can include, for instance, the involvement in activities such as impact monitoring and data collection, depending on the nature and objectives of the CoPs in each Living Lab.

2. Guidelines for stakeholder engagement

The process of stakeholder mapping and engagement in B-WaterSmart takes into account the strategic agenda and objectives defined for the project and its Living Labs, as well as the CoPs Architecture (D1.1). D1.1 provides detailed instructions for the LLs to constitute Communities of Practice within B-WaterSmart, including how to map key stakeholders and organise meetings. In this section of D5.1 we outline key guidelines for a process of stakeholder engagement along three main steps (Figure 4): mapping stakeholders (**step 1: identify**, section 2.1), analyse their concerns, interests and influence networks (**step 2: analyse**, section 2.2) and define objectives for the stakeholder engagement process, according to the socio-economic and environmental context of each territory – using the example of the B-WaterSmart Living Labs; and **step 3: plan** (section 2.3). The mapping and engagement process will, on one hand, seek a coherent approach to discussing cross-cutting issues between different regions, maximising the added value of the interaction between the LLs, and on the other hand take into due account the diversity of socio-economic contexts, through a thorough and regular assessment of their societal challenges, policy gaps and governance issues (section 2.2.1).

Figure 4 - Steps for implementing stakeholder engagement

2.1. Step 1: identify

The identification of the key stakeholders to engage will look at those involved across the water chain, (quality, quantity, drainage, drinking water supply, wastewater management...) primarily, as well as to the main linkages with other sectors (land use, agriculture, planning, energy, etc.) across the nexus water-energy-resources. But it will also require assessing their motivations, core functions, effectiveness and limitations, as well as those with an indirect influence on the water sector.

Besides identifying those already known by the project team, there are other sources of information for the stakeholder mapping, such as policy documents and the ‘snowballing approach’, when the stakeholders already identified are invited to name other possible interested parties. In the case of B-WaterSmart, this ‘snowballing’ and iterative process has followed these key steps:

1. **Preliminary identification of key stakeholders by the project team**, when defining the scope of the CoPs and of the stakeholder mapping (multiple sources, such as policy documents and other material related to the project);
2. **Identification of stakeholders by the Living Lab owners and mentors (through a template circulated by the team)**, taking into account the requirements for each WP
 - a. Identification of CE synergies (e.g., identification of key industries at the local level)
 - b. Identification of key stakeholders already involved in CE-related projects and initiatives;
 - c. Key stakeholders and institutions already involved in direct interaction with the LL owners (municipalities and water utilities);
 - d. Key organisations that will follow the project but are also potential replicators of its solutions;
 - e. Representatives from local organisations and the civil society, fundamental to ensure an adequate consideration of gender, ethnic and other factors in tailoring the solutions to specific local realities and the needs of different social groups, especially most vulnerable ones.
3. **Snowballing method**: ask the CoP participants themselves to identify other relevant stakeholders at the early stage of the engagement process (in meetings and further interactions with the project team)

There are multiple criteria that can be followed when mapping the stakeholders, depending on the objectives of the engagement process itself, and of the project or initiative. The OECD recommends to identify the following stakeholder types, as a matter of principle:

- **primary decision-makers**
- those who are **influential in the area**, community or organisation
- those who have the **power to obstruct decisions**
- those who **have been involved in the issue** in the past.

The stakeholder mapping should include stakeholders with **formal responsibility** and **direct impact** on the decision-making process, but also those with a **material interest**, and those who might be impacted by the project/policy process and/or its outcomes. Beyond those working in the geographical and sectoral areas of the project, those who have knowledge and competencies that might be useful for the process of engagement should also be involved (Hirano & Latorre, 2020) (e.g., representatives from the community who can act as ‘knowledge brokers’ or mediators, those with past experience of similar projects, or those currently involved in similar projects).

Known opponents should also always be involved, in order to promote a broad ownership of the project’s proposals, while taking into account their **needs** and **concerns**. In any case, selection methods should be as transparent as possible, so that everyone understands the criteria for organisation of specific stakeholder groups and their levels of involvement throughout a given research project or initiative.

As a preparation step for further analysis (section 2.2.), the stakeholder map should also take note of the specific **functions** of each stakeholder in terms of service provision, policy making and regulation, as well as analyse the adequacy of current governance settings (e.g., which institutions have tax powers at which administrative scale).

2.2. Step 2: analyse

After a preliminary identification of the key institutions and persons, a further step involves assessing the potential of stakeholders to contribute to or hinder decision-making and implementation processes on water policies/projects, through a more extensive analysis, depending on the specific needs and purposes of each project.

The process of stakeholder analysis involves differentiating and categorising the stakeholders, as well as investigating the relationships between them.

Following up on the identification stage, we need therefore to map other defining characteristics and dynamics of the stakeholders, such as:

- **core governance functions** (strategic planning, policy-making, regulation, financing, service delivery, water resources management, monitoring, evaluation);
- **interactions** (co-ordination, partnership, consultation, information sharing, etc.);
- **interests** in the issue at hand (low - status quo - to high - committed to the process), with possible gaps and overlaps;
- **the scale** at which they operate (local, city, metropolitan, regional, national, EU, global).

A complete stakeholder analysis helps to ensure ownership of the project goals and its credibility by: identifying who has a stake in the planned work; categorising and prioritising stakeholders and with whom there is a need to invest the most time; identifying (and preparing to handle) relationships between stakeholders (whether conflicts or alliances). A successful stakeholder analysis will help the project team to: start talking early to the right people; know what their stakeholders are interested in; find out who has the most influence in terms of helping or hindering project work; find out who is disempowered or marginalised; and identify key relationships (WATER SUM, 2016).

Stakeholder analysis includes identifying stakeholders, establishing their attributes or characteristics, investigating relationships between them, and prioritising who should be involved to what extent in the project. Because stakeholder attributes and dynamics change over time and as a result of the project, stakeholder analysis should be an iterative process that starts at the beginning of a water management initiative and is revisited throughout, helping to guide the planning and implementation.

Formal participation does not equate visibility or having influence, therefore in the stage of stakeholder analysis we should attentively consider how to raise the 'voice' of often less visible social actors and groups, as well as acknowledging underlying conflicts. A thorough stakeholder analysis will assess their relative power, legitimacy and urgency in relation to the matter at discussion (Wood et al 2021).

Issues of representativeness and legitimacy have to be considered - talking to NGOs or local associations, for example, does not necessarily equate to an inclusive engagement, depending on the social context of the research project or initiative. It may be necessary to resort to additional, less structured methods, such as observation or semi-structured interviews to elicit underlying

assumptions, interests, conflicts and power relations that might limit the reach of the engagement process. Dedicating enough time to conduct a careful stakeholder analysis is therefore determinant for the success of the engagement process, and especially so if the research involves sensitive topics or developing countries.

The existent interaction dynamics between stakeholders will vary depending on the sectors involved and on the geographical context. Regular interaction – e.g., through online forums – is essential to promote connectivity and foster a sense of community.

Stakeholder analysis consists of using different rationale, typology/process, and methods for: i) identifying stakeholders; ii) differentiating between and categorising stakeholders; and iii) investigating relationships between stakeholders (Figure 5). Regarding the rationale for stakeholder analysis, Reed et al. (2009) propose three different approaches: 1) the normative approach, 2) the instrumental approach, and 3) the descriptive approach.

Normative approaches, which emphasize the legitimacy of stakeholder engagement and empowerment in decision-making processes, have become more common recently. According to the normative basis, stakeholders should be directly involved in decision-making and have a sense of their own influence over such processes. Instrumental stakeholder research focuses on how organisations should identify, explain, and handle stakeholder actions to achieve desired outcomes. Since it only focuses on defining the relationships between a set of variables, the descriptive approach can be thought of as a warm-up for the normative and instrumental approaches.

The differentiation and categorisation of the stakeholders include methods to characterise and classify stakeholders according to two approaches: i) top-down “analytical categorisations” and; ii) bottom-up “reconstructive methods”.

Analytical categorisations are a set of methods in which classification of stakeholders is carried out by those conducting the analysis based on their observations of a given phenomenon. Interest/influence matrices includes the use of classificatory parameters (e.g., cooperation, competition and threat, and urgency, legitimacy) and the power of these categorisation approaches can be improved by adding further attributes/labels to the stakeholders (e.g., “key players”, “context setters”, “subjects”, “crowd”).

It is worth noting that focusing stakeholder identification on the “usual suspects” can skew the audience, resulting in a lack of representation of marginalised and/or vulnerable groups. Furthermore, since this approach is often used in the absence of direct stakeholder input in the analysis, it may represent mapping the researchers' biases rather than the stakeholders' views, raising concerns about the legitimacy of these categorisations. “Radical transactiveness” focuses on engaging in a two-way dialogue with stakeholders that otherwise be considered peripheral. Many stakeholders who are distant, vulnerable, uninterested, isolated, or non-legitimate, but whose opinions are disruptive, fall into this category. Reconstructive categorisations (“bottom-up”) allow categorisations according to parameters defined by the stakeholders themselves, and the methods used in this approach include stakeholder-led categorisation processes and Q methodology (table 1).

Figure 5 - Rationale, typology, and methods for stakeholder analysis
 (Adapted from Reed et al., 2009)

In the Q methodology stakeholders rank statements according to how much they agree with them, which allows the identification of social discourses and a larger engagement of stakeholders. Strategic Perspectives Analysis (SPA) uses interviews/workshops with stakeholders to define and evaluate the goals of various organisations, as well as the potential challenges and obstacles they face in achieving their objectives, allowing stakeholders to be classified based on their shared objectives.

Deriving from the influence/interest matrices, the Alignment, Interest and Influence Matrix (AIIM) was developed not only to help users to identify the main stakeholders, but also to suggest a possible course of action towards them (Mendizabal & Ramalingam, 2010) (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - The Alignment, Interest and Influence Matrix
(Mendizabal & Ramalingam, 2010)

The AIIM tool is often used in workshops with diverse groups of stakeholders. After defining the objectives of the intervention and carrying out some context analysis (or in-depth research depending on the degree of complexity of the challenge), the AIIM can help clarify where some of the main targets of the interventions stand, namely their objectives and possible influential approaches. This tool is broken down into five steps: 1) classify and list all of the stakeholders who may have an impact on a given outcome; 2) map the stakeholders into a matrix based on their level of alignment and interest, as shown by their discourse, attitudes, and behaviours; 3) think about how you can use this information to engage the various stakeholders; 4) prioritise and understand which of the defined stakeholders has the most influence. The answers to questions about alignment (“do they agree with our approach?”; “Will they concur with our conclusions?” “Do they want to do the same things that we believe are

necessary?") and commitment ("Are they devoting time and money to this subject?"; "Is it their intention for this to happen?"; "Is this something they're talking about?") will determine their position in the matrix (step 2).

The stakeholder-influence network, which can be represented as a "stakeholder influence network diagram," is also derived from influence vs. interest. This technique seeks to surface both the formal and informal relationships that form the foundations of such social networks in a sociogram-like format, considering the multiple and interdependent interactions that exist simultaneously between stakeholders. The network represents stakeholder relationships with connecting arrows, with the direction reflecting the essence of the relationship (with control flowing from the tail to the head) and a double-headed arrow used where they influence each other (Ackermann & Eden, 2011).

The Stakeholder Management Web, which focuses on a single stakeholder analysis, was created to record details about individual key stakeholders' behaviour, goals, and motives in a systematic and informative manner. This approach elicits a more in-depth understanding of the manifest forms of influence (both formal and informal) and bases of concern, which is critical for effective stakeholder management (Ackermann & Eden, 2011).

By recognising the prevailing flows and bottlenecks, as well as the diversity in expertise of various individuals/groups within the system, stakeholder analysis collects the knowledge of different stakeholders through time, people, and place, and aids in grouping stakeholders more efficiently to facilitate co-learning (Reed et al., 2009).

Methods for investigating the relationships between stakeholders and their attributes are summarised on Table 1.

Table 1 - Methods for stakeholder analysis

Method	Description	Sources
Actor-linkage matrices	A common, easy, and adaptable way to depict stakeholder interrelationships. Stakeholders are listed in a table and their connections to one another are depicted using key words (e.g., conflictual, complementary, cooperative, etc).	(Reed et al., 2009)
Interest/influence matrices	The Alignment, Interest and Influence Matrix (AIIM) was developed not only to help users to identify the main stakeholders, but also to suggest a possible course of action towards them.	(Mendizabal & Ramalingam, 2010)
Knowledge mapping	Is a novel method particularly focused on fostering innovation and more flexible than SNA, which can aid the development and diffusion of knowledge within socio-ecological systems.	(Reed et al., 2009)

Q Methodology	Allows to analyse the discourses, conceptual framings and understandings of multiple stakeholders on given issues, by asking them to rank statements according to how much they agree with them, which allows the identification of social discourses and a larger engagement of stakeholders.	(Curry, Barry, & McClenaghan, 2013)
Social network analysis	Employs matrices to arrange data about stakeholder relations, allowing for the recognition of core and marginal stakeholders, as well as how they can be grouped, by using numbers to represent the presence/absence (0,1), strength (e.g., communication, advice, conflict, trust, etc.), and value of the relationships (+/-, 0).	(Reed et al., 2009)
Sociometric analysis	Identify preferred modes of interaction and sources of knowledge amongst stakeholders. This kind of analysis has revealed, for instance, that actors in the water sector have privileged interactions with their peers, tending to create 'silos' of information.	(OECD, 2015)
Radical Transactiveness	Focuses on engaging in a two-way dialogue with stakeholders that otherwise be considered peripheral.	(Reed et al., 2009)
Salience method	Analysis of mapped stakeholders according to three key attributes – power, legitimacy and urgency - in order to make the process of engagement more inclusive and effective.	(Wood et al., 2021)

One aspect to pay attention in the stakeholder analysis is the attributes of actors in relation to the participation process itself. Following on Creighton (2005), Hirano and Latorre (2020) identify four profiles of participants: active (those who will commit the time and energy); commenters (those very interested in the issue, but do not devote much time or other resource); observers (those who read relevant documents, but do not raise voice unless they become very concerned); and apathetic (those who choose not to participate).

Willingness to participate may be affected by multiple factors, and in generally stakeholders and the public will be more motivated to engage if they are directly affected by the changes, such as rises in tariffs, suspicion over water quality or over the transparency of information shared with the public (Hirano & Latorre, 2020). Have experienced directly phenomena associated with climate change, such as extreme events, has revealed determinant in the willingness to change and innovate in water management (Widener et al., 2017).

It is also determinant to consider the social and cultural context, including the place-based stories, memories and emotions held by key actors on the ground (Slobbe, 2020), whenever possible complemented by longitudinal and place-based studies to assess the local and historical context of projects (de Vries, van Bommel, Blackmore, & Asano, 2017). Coastal areas, such as those involved in B-WaterSmart, are par excellence boundary territories to where multiple conflicting interests converge, and therefore it is crucial to take due account of the historical, social and economic circumstances, as well as recent changes to the LL context (Schmidt et al., 2014).

In the case of B-WaterSmart, a round of workshops with the key representatives of the LLs – including municipalities, water utilities and R&D institutions based in the 6 cities and regions – was organised in order to collect information on the main socio-economic factors, social perceptions, potential conflicts and tensions that might be relevant to prepare the stakeholder engagement process.

2.3. Step 3: plan

In planning a process of stakeholder engagement, it is necessary to be aware that all stakeholders need to be regularly informed of the stages and outcomes of a given project, but do not necessarily need to be directly involved at all stages. It is necessary to seek a balance between a comprehensive representation and a manageable number of participants, be it in CoPs or in other modes of interaction with the key actors.

Following the stakeholder analysis, it is essential to discuss stakeholder's expectations and motivations for the engagement process – there might be divergence between the goals of the Project promoters and the degree of influence that some stakeholders might expect to have in the decision-making process, therefore it is of utmost importance to clarify and negotiate these aspects from the start (OECD, 2015). Therefore, it is determinant to start by doing an inventory of questions and expectations amongst participants, in which they can discuss their broad concerns in relation to the sector in question, the critical challenges (present and future) and the key policy and governance issues (Slobbe, 2020).

After identifying the key types of stakeholders to involve, it is crucial to assess their main interests and expectations, in order to ensure a greater impact of the engagement process. An example of a questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose can be found on the [website of CICERONE](#) (2019), a recent H2020 project on Circular Economy.

As a reference, such a questionnaire should collect information on:

- Stakeholder's interests, goals, stakes and potential benefit of innovation in the sector for them
- Stakeholder's expectations from the project
- Stakeholder's concerns, risks and needs
- The project's needs and requests from the stakeholders

In this case, the questionnaire is internal and meant to be filled in by the project partners, as part of the preparation of the stakeholder engagement process. But besides that step, the stakeholders themselves may be invited to discuss their expectations towards the engagement process. In the case of CoPs, the first plenary meeting can be used to define the objectives of the participation process, and even the themes of the following meetings and events (Slobbe, 2020).

Key elements of the stakeholder engagement process

- communication
- consultation
- participation
- representation
- partnerships
- co-decision
- co-production

Source: Stakeholder Engagement for Inclusive Water Governance" (2015), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

There is not a 'one size fits all' when it comes to the organisation of the engagement process. The project team may play a more active role as moderators of the meetings, with more control over the topics discussed and the role of each participant, or else leave scope for the stakeholders to assume greater responsibility, facilitating discussion groups themselves. This will ultimately depend on the overall philosophy of the project for stakeholder and public engagement, as well as its approach to co-creation.

In case of the CoP approach such as the one adopted by B-WaterSmart, and following Slobbe (2020) these are some key steps necessary to create ownership amongst the participants:

- 1) **leave room for them to define the purpose and themes of the CoPs** during the first meetings, as well as discuss their expectations;
- 2) **define rules for participating in the CoPs** (time commitment, whether participants can designate others to substitute them at meetings, etc.) – an example of a CoP protocol is found on D1.1.;
- 3) **provide training when needed**, depending on the themes and activities defined, and attribute roles to participants, who can act as facilitators themselves after the first few meetings (while the CoP organisers maintain a role of 'trouble shooters' when needed).

Other aspect that deserves careful consideration is the **timing** of the interactions, which should be adequate for the different types of stakeholders (for instance NGOs may have limited resources, both human and material, to attend multiple meetings) and the specific role they will have in the project, from an early stage (objective setting, development, implementation). Naturally the participation process will involve costs and a considerable time investment for the institutions conducting the engagement, and therefore there is a need to considerate the trade-offs involved in relation to the purposes fulfilled by engaging with each group of stakeholders. As for the time and resources invested by the stakeholders themselves, these should be pondered, and in some cases even compensated (e.g. transportation costs). Material retribution might be adequate in specific cultural contexts or with large citizen consultations, for instance.

It is crucial to create **multiple opportunities** for engaging smaller audiences so that they have a voice and influence in the decision-making process, fostering empowerment and ownership amongst different groups; these targeted meetings can be balanced with wider communication platforms where different types of stakeholders interact. In the case of B-WaterSmart, the main interaction platforms will be the CoP plenary meetings (once per year), but these will be intercalated by **thematic focus groups** with a smaller number of stakeholders to discuss specific matters of interests. These focus groups will be more frequent and held throughout each year of the project, as described in D1.1. – CoP's Architecture.

Medema et al. (2017) highlight four **types of knowledge** that the stakeholder engagement process should seek to capture: **scientific, experiential, place-based and knowledge deriving from different scales (e.g., local vs regional)**. One of the possible approaches is to identify stakeholders with a low level of knowledge of the sector as a priority target group or the public engagement processes at local and regional level (WATER SUM, 2016).

Figure 7 - Sources of knowledge for co-production
(source: Medema et al., 2017)

Some types of stakeholders may be more difficult to engage and it is determinant to identify from the beginning the conflicts that might arise e.g., competing demands over water resources. Some relations between stakeholders that have been identified as requiring further work are for instance those with agricultural representatives and environment NGOs, decision-makers and researchers (due to the vocabulary employed, etc.).

A crucial part of the planning process is training, as it may be necessary to prepare stakeholders in order to make the participatory process more effective; the governance capacity of stakeholders can be enhanced through processes specifically designed to promote learning and to build competence in understanding the system they want to govern (Megdal, Eden, & Shamir, 2017). When planning engagement activities, it is also important to leave enough space for informal moments, such as lunch breaks, to build trust and confidence between participants (BINGO, 2018).

The emergence of the interdisciplinary field of climate adaptation in research, and the evidence that a strong engagement of stakeholder and the public is critical for the implementation of climate-related policy, has led to further development of multiple participatory methodologies (Schmidt et al., 2018).. In particular, strategies for climate change have given emphasis to visual methods and scenario-building, to foster discussion of possible changes and actions over long time horizons (e.g. 2030, 2050, 2100). Adaptation pathways, which presupposes to identify tipping points beyond which a specific solution will no longer be effective (being then replaced by other options), has been one of the methods most employed as part of adaptation strategies and plans over the last decade, particularly at the regional and local levels, as well as on vulnerable areas (Haasnoot, 2012).

In the context of adaptive water governance, visual methods that involve scenarios and long-term thinking assume especial relevance and will allow to better express uncertainty, as well as vulnerability of the ecosystems and the impacts of policies implemented.

Drawing from the guidelines provided in the MS3 internal report (“Guidelines to operate LL and CoP”) and D1.1 (which includes the stakeholder maps themselves), the strategic objectives and key challenges identified by the LLs in B-WaterSmart, we can outline a process of engagement that defines specific objectives for the participation of each type of stakeholder, as well as their role and level of involvement. The CoP ‘circles’ on table 2 draw from D1.1 and are based on Koti et al. 2017.

Table 2 - Roles and typologies of stakeholders in B-WaterSmart CoPs

Role/ profile	Description	Objective for engaging in CoPs	CoP 'circle' (D1.1)
Partner	This category applies to the partners involved in B-WaterSmart Consortium, either as part of a Living Lab or participating/leading the work packages, as well as third parties	Develop BWS products (technologies and tools); build capacity	Core
Core co-creator	Actors and organisations that are core to the development of the B-WaterSmart solutions, which have a central role and/or influence at the all levels, either in terms of the social acceptance of the solutions (e.g. neighbourhood associations) or by directly participating in circular opportunities and business models and the further development of water-smart solutions (e.g. sectoral organisations, agriculture and industry, municipalities, regional/local authorities)	Active participate in the development of BWS innovative solutions/products; Raise awareness; Improve social acceptance and implementation; build capacity; manage conflicts	Core + Active
Collaborator	Actors and organisations that are core to the development of policies and decision-making related to developing Circular Economy in the water sector. This category includes policy and decision-makers such as Environment Agencies and regulators	Overcome policy gaps; support implementation and development of policies and decision-making	Active
Follower	Actors and organisations beyond current geographical scope of BWS LL which will participate in the workshops or dissemination events, to gain a in-depth knowledge of BWS solutions and have the explicit intention of applying them in their respective sectors/areas of intervention (e.g. municipalities, water utilities, companies or sectoral associations in other regions/countries)	Find and develop technical solutions; ensure the replicability, continuity and impact of B-WaterSmart	Active - Peripheral
Observer	Actors and organisations participating in the workshops or dissemination events who follow the co-creation process but do not actively participate in it (e.g., government institutions, local associations)	Attends meetings, follows co-creation process, and participates in discussion of overarching and general issues.	Peripheral

2.3.1. Communication channels and participatory methodologies

Typically the stakeholder engagement process will involve multiple channels of interaction, in articulation with the communication strategy for public engagement, which in the case of B-WaterSmart pertains to WP7.

We can distinguish multiple channels and methods, which will operate in articulation, contributing a cumulative base of information on perceptions, views, diagnoses and suggestions to address challenges in the sector. Furthermore, each of these moments of interaction will provide useful inputs to plan and prepare the following stakeholder meetings, as well as the reports and policy recommendations delivered by the project.

In the case of B-WaterSmart, the deliverable D1.1 is the reference document for the selection of participatory methodologies to be applied in the CoP meetings. There will be at least a plenary meeting per year in each LL, and multiple 'focus groups' meetings with a smaller number of participants and specific themes and objectives defined. These will feed information into the general CoP meetings and help support the overall outcomes of the engagement process, as well as ultimately the co-creation of the innovative water-smart solutions. This engagement process is meant to have continuity in each city and region involved, giving way to innovative modes of water governance in each territory.

Besides the tools employed by the communication team or work package, which are meant for public engagement and dissemination for a wider audience (e.g. regular newsletter, website, social media), there should be a permanent platform for interacting and sharing documentation with the key stakeholders. Ideally, this online platform would be maintained beyond the term of the project as a key node for interaction among stakeholders (as CoP members, for instance) and also used for organising online meetings and workshops. It is therefore fundamental that it allows to make presentations, create and manage discussion 'break-out' rooms, as well as enable stakeholders to upload information and

Communication channels

- **Interviews**

Allow stakeholders to speak confidentially and more freely about issues that might be controversial; build personal relations with stakeholders

- **Focus groups**

Allow a smaller group of between 8 and 15 people to provide their views and opinions of targeted baseline information

- **Surveys**

Monitor the impact of the project, analyse perceptions and views on the challenges of the field, as well as on the solutions developed by the project; gather baseline data

- **Meetings**

Meetings with specific stakeholders, for instance government institutions to provide follow-up on the project and contribute to policy design

Use of sectoral associations and platforms to complement interaction with stakeholders from different groups, such as companies

proposals, send direct messages and pose questions to the team and the other participants. This will help create ownership of the project and keep the momentum and interaction dynamic between meetings and events, as well as provide a permanent source of information on the project, ongoing debates and proposals.

In selecting this platform, it is necessary to take into consideration the procedures for protection of personal data (see section 3), as well as safety of data storage, according to the project Data Management Plan. Moreover, it is fundamental to plan for the necessary number of users and attendants, which may expand, during the project, to several hundreds. It is advisable to have a subscription contract that allows secure and sufficient data storage and maintenance, and in some cases, when applicable, this platform can be developed by a partner from the project consortium.

KWR has compiled a list with description of offline and online engagement tools and moderation techniques that can be used at B-WaterSmart CoPs (D1.1. – CoPs architecture). The LL owners and mentors will organise and manage CoPs at the local level and in the local languages, drawing from the orientations of D1.1. As part of T1.2 activities, the project team will support LLs in the design and organisation of CoP meetings, in particular in the selection of the most appropriate engagement tools and moderation techniques for the meetings. Table 3 presents examples and general guidelines according to the objectives and expected outcomes for each phase of the engagement plan.

Table 3 - Participatory tools and techniques

Objectives	Stakeholder groups/roles	Techniques & tools	Outcomes
Collecting information CoP preparation	Key institutions and organisations previously identified by LL owners and mentors; followers (signed letters)	Surveys Focus groups (sub-CoPs/specific stakeholder groups e.g. farmers) Semi-structured interviews Informal conversations Online meetings (2021)	Consolidated & detailed stakeholder map Plan CoPs & BWS engagement process according to stakeholder's expectations and concerns
Promote discussion, collaborative work and co-production	Co-creators Collaborators	Survey and polls tools (e.g. group map, Mentimeter) Web meeting platforms (e.g. Zoom, Microsoft Teams) Collaborative online tools (e.g. Mural, Miro, Groupmap, Google Jamboard)	Develop ownership the Project solutions amongst stakeholders Co-develop solutions for policy & regulation gaps Explore/prepare innovative governance models

Monitor the progress and impact of CoP's work	ALL groups	Surveys (offline or online) Google forms Mentimeter; Slido (during meetings)	Continuous improvement of CoPs activities and results Stimulate social learning
Share documentation and collaborate in between meetings	ALL groups Co-creators Collaborators	Google Docs, Microsoft Teams Nextcloud? (separate from Project access)	Detailed outputs and documentation to support preparation of CoP meetings
Training and awareness-raising on specific water-related issues (e.g., water reuse)	In articulation with INALLs Identify groups at the local level – e.g. NGOs and local neighbourhood associations Followers	Webinar platforms In-person workshops Field visits	Raise awareness of water issues Stimulate social learning Build capacity amongst stakeholders to act as co-creators of water-smart solutions

(Adapted from KWR, “Community of Practice Guidance for design, implementation and evaluation”, D1.1)

There are other useful resources online that can be easily adapted to different H2020 projects on sustainability and circular economy, for instance the Action Catalogue of stakeholder engagement methodologies (currently 57), which allows to filter the contents by type of stakeholder involved and level of involvement (e.g., participation in data collection): <http://actioncatalogue.eu/>. The Engage2020 Action Catalogue is an online decision support tool that is intended to enable researchers, policy-makers and others wanting to conduct inclusive research, to find the method that is best suited for their specific project needs. It will be made publicly available so that anyone can search the methods, read thorough descriptions of what the methods do, strengths and weaknesses of each, what societal challenges they can be used to address, and examples of what they have been used for previously and much more. The Action Catalogue is made easily searchable, so as to make finding the method best suited for a project, intuitive and fast.

3. Ethical issues: check list and key resources

D1.1 – CoPs Architecture – details the ethical procedures to be followed in the B-WaterSmart project specifically. Here we opt for presenting an ‘ethics check list’ and the key resources that can be consulted in order to plan an ethics assessment and plan for similar projects, according to current legislation and regulation on protection of personal data and other ethical issues that may be applicable in each case.

Any process of stakeholder engagement will have to be planned in respect of the EU Regulations on ethical procedures and personal data protection, namely the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The specific procedures for handling and storing data in a H2020 project, including sensitive data, have to be outlined in a [Data Management Plan](#), which in the case of B-WaterSmart is D8.3 (first version released in February 2021 and available at the project website). Stakeholders have to be informed of the specific purposes for which their data will be collected, in which cases they may be published and in what form, and of all the procedures undertaken to avoid exposure of personal data, namely protected storage, aggregation and anonymization (ALLEA, 2017; European Commission, 2018a).

In accordance with the GDPR, each person has to give previous and informed consent to any data collection, including specific consent for capture of sound and image. For this purpose, the project team has to prepare specific consent forms to be signed by the stakeholders. In the case of B-WaterSmart, these documents were included as Annexes of D1.1 in May 2021. It is estimated that the first CoP meetings will be held online in October 2021.

The stakeholder database, for the purpose of organising meetings and sending invitations, has to comply with the GDPR, which requires that only stakeholders that have officially submitted consent for these purposes are contacted by the project team. A GDPR compliant form has to be sent (see D1.1 for the B-WaterSmart template) specifying the purposes of collecting each data, including all personal details (such as full name, address and phone contacts, email), their storage conditions and duration and the contacts of the responsible person in case the stakeholders wishes to exert their ARCO rights and change or withdraw their information.

Table 4 - Ethics procedures and sources

Topic	Key resources	Tasks
General ethics issues and procedures (all EU languages)	<p>European Commission (2019), Guide on how to complete a H2020 Ethics Self-Assessment</p> <p>ALLEA (2017). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity</p>	Identify the ethical issues that are applicable to the Project, including those concerning human dignity, individual rights and social justice, ensuring non-discrimination and inclusiveness
Data collection, handling, management & storage	<p>OpenAIRE, How to make your data FAIR (online resource, guides for researchers)</p> <p>European Commission (2018b) Turning FAIR into reality (report)</p> <p>European Commission (2016), Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020</p>	Define the type of data to collect, how they will be stored, managed and shared; define procedures for anonymization of personal data, access rights and revision
Protection of personal data	<p>European Commission. (2018a). Ethics and data protection.</p> <p>General Data Protection Regulation (2018) – legal text</p>	Consent forms + information sheet (general for data + image and sound);
Transferring data from/to non-EU countries	<p>European Commission (2021) – Data Protection (FAQ) (online)</p>	Verify whether these countries have an agreement with the EU; specify procedures to be followed in case there is not

4. Conclusions

Following up on Milestone 3 of B-WaterSmart (internal report); D4.1 and D1.1 – CoP Architecture and Stakeholder Mapping, D5.1 has provided an overview of the state of the art and best practices for implementing an adaptive governance in sustainability projects, in the water sector and along the nexus water-energy-resources. This deliverable has included an introductory review of the literature on stakeholder engagement and adaptive water governance, which has outlined the key challenges and developments in research and policy in sustainability projects, in face of the challenges of climate adaptation and the circular economy.

The second part of the document – sections 2 and 3 – offer more concrete guidelines, drawing from the literature, as well as the example of B-WaterSmart and other H2020 projects, on how to identify stakeholder, attribute specific roles to different actors in the engagement process, define objectives for their involvement and select participatory methodologies. This without forgetting the ethical issues that have to be taken into consideration, and the procedures that will have to be followed, providing a check list with some useful resources to consult.

This report has intended to reach a wider audience of policy-makers, researchers, practitioners and interested public, by providing best practices and guidelines that can be applied to a diversity of projects involving processes of stakeholder engagement. It is clear nowadays that we are at a turning point in preparing our local communities to face the challenges of climate change, pollution and water scarcity over the coming decade and beyond. B-WaterSmart aims at supporting the implementation of the EU Action Plan for Circular Economy, the Green Deal and the new EU Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change.

5. References

- Ackermann, F., & Eden, C. (2011). Strategic Management of Stakeholders: Theory and Practice. *Long Range Planning*, 44(3), 179–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2010.08.001>
- Akhmouch, A., & Clavreul, D. (2016). Stakeholder engagement for inclusive water governance: “Practicing what we preach” with the OECD water governance initiative. *Water*, 8(5), 204.
- Avdishchenko, A. (2018). "Toward a Circular Economy Regional Monitoring Framework for European Regions: Conceptual Approach", *Sustainability* 10, 12: 4398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124398>
- Anzaldúa G., Gerner N. V., Lago M., Abhold K., Hinzmann M., Beyer S., Winking C., Riegels N., Krogsgaard Jensen J., Termes M., Amorós J., Wencki K., Strehl C., Ugarelli R., Hasenheit M., Nafo I., Hernandez M., Vilanova E., Damman S., Brouwer S., Rouillard J., Schwesig D., Birk S. (2018): Getting into the water with the Ecosystem Services Approach: The DESSIN ESS evaluation framework. *Ecosystem Services*, 30, 318-326.
- ALLEA (2017). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*. Berlin: European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities. Available at: <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>
- Bellezoni, R. A. et al. (2021) Understanding and conceptualizing how urban green and blue infrastructure affects the food, water, and energy nexus: A synthesis of the literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, [s. l.], v. 289, DOI 10.1016
- Benson, D. et al. (2020): Moving beyond water centrality? Conceptualizing integrated water resources management for implementing sustainable development Goals. *Sustainability Science* (2020) 15:671–681, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00733-5>
- BINGO (2018). *Guidelines designed to create, feed and enhance “win-win” collaborations between researchers and stakeholders*. Available at: <http://www.projectbingo.eu/output/guidelines>
- Bouwma I., Schleyer C., Primmer E., Winkler K. J., Berry P., Young J., Carmen E., Špulerová J., Bezák P., Preda E., Vadineanu A. (2018): Adoption of the ecosystem services concept in EU policies. *Ecosystem Services*, 29, 213-222.
- Breukers, S., & Jeuken, Y. (DuneWorks) (2017): Step-by-step guide for co-production and co-creation of nature-based solutions, Nature4Cities.
- Camilleri, M. A. (2020). European environment policy for the circular economy: Implications for business and industry stakeholders. *Sustainable Development*, 28(6), 1804-1812. doi:10.1002/sd.2113
- Chaffin, B. C., Gosnell, H., & Cosens, B. A. (2014). A decade of adaptive governance scholarship: synthesis and future directions. *Ecology and society*, 19(3). doi:10.5751/es-06824-190356

- CICERONE. (2019). D4.1 Stakeholder Engagement Action Plan. Available at: <http://cicerone-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/CICERONE-D4.1-Stakeholder-Engagement-Action-Plan.pdf>
- Cosens, B., & Gunderson, L. H. (2018). Adaptive Water Governance: Summary and Synthesis. In B. Cosens & L. H. Gunderson (Eds.), *Practical Panarchy for Adaptive Water Governance* (pp. 313-322). Cham: Springer.
- Conallin, J. C., Dickens, C., Hearne, D., & Allan, C. (2017). Chapter 7 - Stakeholder Engagement in Environmental Water Management. In A. C. Horne, J. A. Webb, M. J. Stewardson, B. Richter, & M. Acreman (Eds.), *Water for the Environment* (pp. 129-150): Academic Press.
- Curry, R., Barry, J., & McClenaghan, A. (2013). Northern Visions? Applying Q methodology to understand stakeholder views on the environmental and resource dimensions of sustainability. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 56(5), 624-649.
- de Vries, J., van Bommel, S., Blackmore, C., & Asano, Y. (2017). Where There Is No History: How to Create Trust and Connection in Learning for Transformation in Water Governance. *Water*, 9(2), 130. doi:10.3390/w9020130
- Dilling, L., & Lemos, M. C. (2011). Creating usable science: Opportunities and constraints for climate knowledge use and their implications for science policy. *Global Environmental Change*, 21(2), 680-689. doi:10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.11.006
- Dillon, P., Fernández Escalante, E., Megdal, S.B. und Massmann, G. (2020) Managed Aquifer Recharge for Water Resilience. *Water* 12(7), 1846.
- EurEau (2020): The governance of water services in Europe. EurEau, The European Federation of National Associations of Water Services, Brussels.
- European Commission. (2018a). Ethics and data protection. Brussels: EC. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf
- European Commission (2018b) Turning FAIR into reality: final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data. Brussels: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/s/pkIC>
- European Commission (2019) Horizon 2020: Guidance on how to complete your ethics self-assessment. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf
- European Commission (2020a) A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe (COM/2020/98), Brussels: EC. Available online at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>
- European Commission (2020b): Nature-Based Solutions: State of the Art in EU-funded Projects, edited by Tom Wild, Tiago Freitas and Sofie Vandewoestijne, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Brussels.

- European Commission (2021) Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (COM/2021/82). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:82:FIN>
- European Environment Agency (2020) CICES - Towards a common classification of ecosystem services, <https://cices.eu/>
- Fletcher, T. D., Shuster, W., Hunt, W. F., Ashley, R., Butler, D., Arthur, S., Trowsdale, S., Barraud, S., Semadeni-Davies, A., Bertrand-Krajewski, J-L., Mikkelsen, P. S., Rivard, G., Uhl, M., Dagenais, D., & Viklander, M. (2015). SUDS, LID, BMPs, WSUD and more - The evolution and application of terminology surrounding urban drainage. *Urban Water Journal*, 12(7), 525-542. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062x.2014.916314>
- Folke, C., Berkes, F., & Colding, J. (1998). Ecological practices and social mechanisms for building resilience and sustainability. *Linking social and ecological systems: Management practices and social mechanisms for building resilience*, 414-436.
- Gerner N. V., Nafu I., Winking C., Wencki K., Strehl C., Wortberg T., Niemann A., Anzaldua G., Lago M., Birk S. (2018): Large-scale river restoration pays off: A case study of ecosystem service valuation for the Emscher restoration generation project. *Ecosystem Services*, 30, 327-338.
- Haasnoot, M., Middelkoop, H., Offermans, A. et al. (2012) Exploring pathways for sustainable water management in river deltas in a changing environment. *Climatic Change*, 115, 795–819. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-012-0444-2>
- Hirano, M., & Latorre, C. (2020). *Guidelines for Public Participation in the Regulation of Urban Water Services*. Available at: <https://iwa-network.org/publications/guidelines-for-public-participation-in-the-regulation-of-urban-water-services/>
- Horizon 2020 Expert Group (2015). Towards an EU research and innovation policy agenda for nature-based solutions & re-naturing cities: final report of the Horizon 2020 expert group on 'Nature-based solutions and re-naturing cities'. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/s/pkn2>
- Huitema, D., Mostert, E., Egas, W., Moellenkamp, S., Pahl-Wostl, C., & Yalcin, R. (2009). Adaptive Water Governance: Assessing the Institutional Prescriptions of Adaptive (Co-)Management from a Governance Perspective and Defining a Research Agenda. *Ecology and society*, 14(26), [online]
- Hutchins, K., Lindenfeld, L., Bell, K., Leahy, J., & Silka, L. (2013). Strengthening Knowledge Co-Production Capacity: Examining Interest in Community-University Partnerships. *Sustainability*, 5(9), 3744-3770. doi:10.3390/su5093744
- Jiménez, A., Saikia, P., Giné, R., Avello, P., Leten, J., Liss Lymer, B., . . . Ward, R. (2020). Unpacking Water Governance: A Framework for Practitioners. *Water*, 12(3), 827. doi:10.3390/w12030827
- Lemos, M. C. (2015). Usable climate knowledge for adaptive and co-managed water governance. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 12, 48-52. doi:10.1016/j.cosust.2014.09.005

- Lokesh, K., Ladu, L., & Summerton, L. (2018). Bridging the Gaps for a 'Circular' Bioeconomy: Selection Criteria, Bio-Based Value Chain and Stakeholder Mapping. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1695. doi:10.3390/su10061695
- Lundmark, C., & Jonsson, G. (2013). Prospects for learning in river management: exploring the initial implementation of the Water Framework Directive in a Swedish river basin. *Environmental Education Research*, 20(2), 161-176. doi:10.1080/13504622.2013.780585
- McNie, E. C. (2013). Delivering Climate Services: Organizational Strategies and Approaches for Producing Useful Climate-Science Information. *Weather Climate and Society*, 5(1), 14-26.
- Medema, W., Adamowski, J., Orr, C., Furber, A., Wals, A., & Milot, N. (2017). Building a Foundation for Knowledge Co-Creation in Collaborative Water Governance: Dimensions of Stakeholder Networks Facilitated through Bridging Organizations. *Water*, 9(1), 60. doi:10.3390/w9010060
- Megdal, S., Eden, S., & Shamir, E. (2017). Water Governance, Stakeholder Engagement, and Sustainable Water Resources Management. *Water*, 9(3), 190. doi:10.3390/w9030190
- Mendizabal, E. (2010). The Alignment, Interest and Influence Matrix (AIIM) Toolkit. Research and Policy in Development (RAPID), Overseas Development Institute (ODI): London, UK. Available at: <https://www.odi.org/publications/5288-stakeholder-engagement-stakeholder-analysis-aiim-alignment-interest-influence-matrix-roma>
- Nesshöver, C., Assmuth, T., Irvine, K. N., Rusch, G. M., Waylen, K. A., Delbaere, B., ... & Wittmer, H. (2017). The science, policy and practice of nature-based solutions: An interdisciplinary perspective. *Science of the total environment*, 579, 1215-1227.
- Nicholson-Cole, S., & O'Riordan, T. (2009). Adaptive governance for a changing coastline: science, policy and the public in search of a sustainable future. In N. W. Adger, I. Lorenzoni, & K. O'Brien, (eds.) (Eds.), *Adapting to climate change: thresholds, values, governance*. . Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- OECD (2015). Mapping water-related stakeholders at all levels. *Stakeholder Engagement for Inclusive Water Governance*. Paris.
- OECD (2020), The Circular Economy in Cities and Regions: Synthesis Report, OECD Urban Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/10ac6ae4-en>.
- Özerol, G., Vinke-de Kruijf, J., Brisbois, M. C., Casiano Flores, C., Deekshit, P., Girard, C., . . . Schröter, B. (2018). Comparative studies of water governance: a systematic review. *Ecology and society*, 23(4). doi:10.5751/es-10548-230443
- Padilla-Rivera, Alejandro, Sara Russo-Garrido, and Nicolas Merveille (2020). Addressing the Social Aspects of a Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 12, no. 19: 7912. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12197912>
- Pahl-Wostl, C. (2017). An Evolutionary Perspective on Water Governance: From Understanding to Transformation. *Water Resources Management*, 31(10), 2917-2932. doi:10.1007/s11269-017-1727-1
- Pahl-Wostl, C. (2019). Governance of the water-energy-food security nexus: A multi-level coordination challenge. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 92, 356-367. doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2017.07.017

- Palomo-Rios, L., Vandewoestijne, S. (2021). Evaluating the Impact of Nature-based Solutions: A Handbook for Practitioners, European Commission. <https://oppla.eu/sites/default/files/uploads/evaluating-impact-nature-based-solutions-handbook-practitioners.pdf>
- Potschin, M. and R. Haines-Young (2016): Defining and measuring ecosystem services. In: Potschin, M., Haines-Young, R., Fish, R. and Turner, R.K. (eds) Routledge Handbook of Ecosystem Services. Routledge, London and New York, pp. 25-44. Available from: <http://www.routledge.com/books/details/9781138025080/>
- Romano, O., & Akhmouch, A. (2019). Water Governance in Cities: Current Trends and Future Challenges. *Water*, 11(3), 500. doi:10.3390/w11030500
- Reed, M. S. (2008). Stakeholder participation for environmental management: a literature review. *Biological conservation*, 141(10), 2417-2431.
- Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C. H., & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(5), 1933–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>
- Schlosberg, D., Collins, L. B., & Niemeyer, S. (2017). Adaptation policy and community discourse: risk, vulnerability, and just transformation. *Environmental Politics*, 26(3), 413-437. doi:10.1080/09644016.2017.1287628
- Schmidt, L., Gomes, C., Guerreiro, S., & O'Riordan, T. (2014). Are we all on the same boat? The challenge of adaptation facing Portuguese coastal communities: Risk perception, trust-building and genuine participation. *Land Use Policy*, 38, 355-365. doi:DOI 10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.11.008
- Schmidt L., Alves A.F., Valente S., Mourato J.M. (2018) Outlining Community Perceptions of Climate Change in Local Adaptation Strategies Development: The Case of ClimAdaPT.Local. In: Alves F., Leal Filho W., Azeiteiro U. (eds) *Theory and Practice of Climate Adaptation*. Climate Change Management. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72874-2_13
- Scott, C. A., Shrestha, P. P., & Lutz-Ley, A. N. (2020). The re-adaptation challenge: limits and opportunities of existing infrastructure and institutions in adaptive water governance. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 44, 104-112. doi:10.1016/j.cosust.2020.09.012
- Slobbe, E. v. (2020). Communities of practice in the field of water and climate. Experiments with new forms of connectivity between experts, scientists and stakeholders
- Stuchtey, M. (2015). Rethinking the water cycle . McKinsey & Company Insights & Publications. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/sustainability/our-insights/rethinking-the-water-cycle>
- Walker, B., Holling, C. S., Carpenter, S. R., & Kinzig, A. (2004). Resilience, Adaptability and Transformability in Social-ecological Systems. *Ecology and society*, 9(2)(5), [online].

- WATER SUM. (2016). *Stakeholder Analysis for Integrated Water Resources Management*. Retrieved from Szentendre, Hungary:
- WFD (2000): Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for the Community action in the field of water policy
- Widener, J. M., Gliedt, T. J., & Hartman, P. (2017). Visualizing dynamic capabilities as adaptive capacity for municipal water governance. *Sustain Sci*, 12(2), 203-219. doi:10.1007/s11625-016-0408-y
- Wood DJ, Mitchell RK, Agle BR, Bryan LM. Stakeholder Identification and Saliency After 20 Years: Progress, Problems, and Prospects. *Business & Society*. 2021;60(1):196-245. doi:10.1177/0007650318816522
- Zölch, T. et al. Regulating urban surface runoff through nature-based solutions – An assessment at the micro-scale. *Environmental Research*, [s. l.], v. 157, p. 135–144, 2017. DOI 10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.023.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869171. The publication reflects only the authors' views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.